

Full Length Research Paper

An earth-eco socialist approach towards sustainable e-waste management in Lagos State

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Received 28 May, 2025; Accepted 18 July, 2025

Electronic waste (e-waste) poses an escalating threat to both human and environmental health in Nigeria, particularly in Lagos State, which has become a major hub for the accumulation and informal processing of used electronics. This paper investigates the structural drivers, health risks, and governance failures surrounding e-waste in Lagos and proposes an ethical alternative grounded in Earth-Eco-Socialism. Using a critical, qualitative literature review approach, the study synthesizes findings across environmental science, public health, and political economy. It reveals how poverty, global trade imbalances, and inadequate regulation perpetuate a cycle of pollution and inequality. The analysis shows that Lagos's e-waste crisis disproportionately harms marginalized communities and ecosystems. By applying an Earth-Eco-Socialist framework that blends eco-socialist critique with communal ethics and recognition of nature's intrinsic value, the paper outlines justice-centered strategies such as cooperative waste management, global corporate accountability, and participatory environmental governance. The study concludes that Earth-Eco-Socialism offers a holistic, morally grounded approach to sustainable e-waste solutions in the Global South.

Key words: E-waste management, environmental sustainability, earth-eco-socialism, public health, electronic waste policy.

INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for information and communication technology (ICT) devices and other electronic gadgets, especially at low prices, has turned Nigeria into a major destination for used and discarded electronics (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2019).

These products often end up as electronic waste (e-waste)-discarded electrical and electronic equipment such as computers, refrigerators, televisions, mobile phones, and other devices. While e-waste poses

challenges globally, the issue is particularly severe in developing countries like Nigeria, where a lack of appropriate technology and infrastructure makes proper disposal and recycling difficult. Estimates indicate that over 57 million metric tons of e-waste was generated worldwide in 2021, with projections exceeding 70 million tons by 2030 (Adepitan et al., 2023) (Figure 1).

Nigeria, as the most populous country in Africa, receives a substantial portion of this waste. For example,

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Figure 1. Projected annual production of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) through 2030.
Source: Adepitan et al. (2023).

about 71,000 tonnes of used electronic goods enter Nigeria each year through Lagos's ports (UNEP, 2019), contributing to an ever-growing e-waste stream.

Despite the urgent need for action, responses from authorities in Nigeria have been inadequate. E-waste imports and local generation continue largely unchecked, leading to environmental contamination and public health hazards.

Improper e-waste handling, such as open burning and crude recycling releases toxins into air, soil, and water, which have been linked to respiratory illnesses, neurological disorders, and other diseases in exposed populations (Ghulam and Abushammala, 2023; Okukpon, 2015). Effective e-waste management is therefore not only an environmental necessity but also a public health imperative.

Nigeria requires a strong theoretical and policy framework to guide sustainable e-waste management. This paper proposes an Earth-Eco-Socialist approach, which emphasizes the fair distribution of benefits and burdens, the protection of human and environmental health, and a commitment to sustainability and social justice. Earth-Eco-Socialism is an ethical paradigm that blends ecological consciousness with socialist principles to address environmental crises in Africa.

It challenges the capitalist exploitation of nature by asserting a duty of care toward the ecosystem and equitable stewardship of resources. By contextualizing e-waste management within this framework, the study aims to highlight how reorienting values and policies can help resolve Lagos State's e-waste challenges. The following outlines the methodology of this critical literature review, then presents and discusses the findings on Lagos's e-waste problem - its magnitude, drivers, stakeholder roles, and impacts, and finally illustrates how the Earth-Eco-Socialist framework can offer solutions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employed a qualitative, critical literature review methodology (Wright and Michailova, 2022; Gheondea, 2015) to explore the systemic challenges and justice implications of electronic waste (e-waste) management in Lagos State, Nigeria. This approach was selected due to its flexibility in accommodating an interdisciplinary scope and evolving themes within the subject matter. Given that e-waste intersects public health, environmental science, urban governance, political economy, and social justice, this approach allowed for the use of diverse strategies in identifying and selecting relevant sources. It facilitated engagement with a wide range of materials - from empirical studies and policy documents to theoretical frameworks and case reports, enabling a

creative and holistic synthesis of knowledge. This flexibility was particularly valuable in tracing the interlinked drivers of e-waste proliferation and in incorporating normative perspectives like Earth-Eco-Socialism. Moreover, the iterative nature of the narrative review allowed the research to adapt as new insights emerged, supporting the refinement of focus and the pursuit of thematic connections across the literature. As a result, the review process was not constrained by rigid inclusion/exclusion criteria but rather was guided by conceptual relevance and depth of contribution to the identified themes.

The review drew on secondary data, including peer-reviewed journal articles, case studies, national and international policy documents, regulatory instruments, news outlets and other grey literature published largely between 2015 and 2025. Literature was sourced through academic databases including Google Scholar, ScienceDirect, and targeted searches via Google. Search terms included combinations of keywords such as “e-waste Nigeria,” “Lagos electronic waste,” “environmental justice,” “eco-socialism and waste management” and “sustainable e-waste management.” Boolean operators (AND, OR) were used to refine searches, and the process was conducted iteratively to capture emerging themes and relevant subtopics. Sources were selected purposively based on their relevance to six core thematic areas:

- i) The definition and scope of e-waste;
- ii) The scale and nature of e-waste generation in Lagos;
- iii) Socioeconomic drivers of e-waste proliferation;
- iv) Health and environmental impacts of improper e-waste disposal;
- v) Governance structures and regulatory gaps; and
- vi) Theoretical frameworks for sustainability and environmental justice, with a focus on Earth-Eco-Socialism.

A thematic coding approach was used to organize and analyze the literature. Data from selected sources were grouped under the guiding themes, allowing for synthesis and triangulation of findings across different types of documents.

Emphasis was placed on integrating existing empirical evidence with normative perspectives to assess both the realities of e-waste in Lagos and the adequacy of current responses. The Earth-Eco-Socialist lens, grounded in the ethical imperatives of sustainability, social equity, and ecological stewardship, informed the interpretive framework for evaluating the literature.

While narrative reviews do not follow a rigid systematic protocol, efforts were made to ensure breadth and depth of coverage, minimize selection bias, and maintain analytical coherence. The use of diverse, multidisciplinary sources and the alignment of findings under consistent themes strengthened the credibility and policy relevance of the review's conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

E-Waste challenges in Lagos State

Lagos State has emerged as the epicenter of e-waste generation and accumulation in Nigeria, reflecting both global trends and local factors. As Nigeria's economic and technological hub, Lagos attracts a high volume of electronic goods and, consequently, a disproportionate share of the nation's e-waste (Ogunyemi and Marinho, 2025). Rapid urbanization, population growth, and increasing consumer demand for electronics contribute to the rising waste stream. Studies indicate that Nigeria is among the most e-waste-contaminated countries in Africa, receiving over four million units of computers and

other electronic waste annually (Ogunyemi and Marinho, 2025). Lagos alone accounts for a significant share, regularly receiving large consignments of end-of-life electronics from abroad. Estimates suggest that as much as 500,000 tonnes of e-waste enter the country each month through the Lagos port (Ogunyemi and Marinho, 2025; Abogunrin-Olafisoye and Adeyi, 2025).

Lagos's e-waste sector is centered on seven main hubs, including Alaba International Market, Ojota Scrap Market, Ikeja Computer Village, Lawanson Market, Westminster Market, as well as the Olusosun and Solous dumpsites (Ogunyemi and Marinho, 2025). Among these, Ikeja and Alaba stand out as the most prominent, acting as key entry points for e-waste shipments originating from the United States and Europe (Issah et al., 2022). The Alaba site, in particular, is recognized as one of Africa's largest and most established centers for dismantling, refurbishing, and recycling obsolete electronics (Anselm et al., 2021).

Roughly 77% of Nigeria's imported e-waste originates from the European Union, often consisting of devices at or near the end of their lifespan (Baldé et al., 2015; Woggsborg and Schröder, 2018). Lax enforcement of import regulations under the Basel Convention means that container loads of obsolete computers, televisions, and other gadgets enter Lagos under the guise of second-hand goods (UNEP, 2019). These imports, combined with the high turnover of electronics in use locally, result in thousands of tonnes of e-waste piling up in the metropolis each year.

Informal processing of e-waste dominates Lagos's waste management landscape. By 2010, an estimated 80% of e-waste recycling in Nigeria occurred in the informal sector, and this pattern persists today (Baldé et al., 2015). In sites like the Olusosun dump and Ikeja scrapyards, informal recyclers and scavengers manually dismantle devices or burn off insulation to extract valuable metals (UNEP, 2019). These rudimentary methods expose workers and nearby communities to hazardous substances such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and brominated flame retardants (Okukpon, 2015; Ghulam and Abushammala, 2023). At Alaba International Market, soil testing in 2024 revealed elevated concentrations of lead, cadmium, chromium, nickel, copper, and zinc - posing serious ecological risks (Bankole et al., 2024; Owen et al., 2025). Another local study found cancer risk indices as high as 183 among adults and children in Lagos's recycling zones (Adeyi et al., 2019).

Hence, environmental and health hazards from these substances - such as lead, cadmium, mercury, and brominated flame retardants, are widely reported and often tied to burning and rudimentary dismantling practices. A 2025 assessment of West African disposal sites further emphasizes that e-waste pollution is linked to critical health issues, including infant mortality near dump sites (Lovo and Rawlings, 2025). This current and

worsening situation is corroborated by recent observations that reveal that Lagos's Apapa and Tincan Island ports still remain key gateways for used electronic equipment, with substantial imports continuing despite Basel Convention restrictions (Ibrahim and Nasiru, 2024). Consequently, environmental degradation is severe: soil and groundwater are contaminated by heavy metals leaching from dumps, and open burning of plastics contributes to air pollution and associated health problems.

Public health impacts include higher incidences of respiratory illnesses, neurological damage, and other chronic conditions in areas surrounding e-waste dumps (Abogunrin-Olafisoye and Adeyi, 2025; Omole et al., 2015; Hossain et al., 2010). Together, these findings confirm that the combination of large volumes of imported e-waste, ubiquitous informal processing, and weak regulation has made Lagos one of the continent's most polluted e-waste hotspots.

Drivers of the E-Waste crisis in Lagos

Multiple interrelated factors drive the prevalence of e-waste in Lagos. One primary factor is poverty and the economic incentive it creates for importing and scavenging electronic waste. As of 2024, nearly 47% of Nigerians - approximately 128.6 million people out of a population of 273.7 million - live in poverty, according to World Bank estimates (Worldometers, 2025; World Bank, 2024). This figure reflects those living below the international extreme poverty threshold of \$2.15 per person per day, underscoring the depth of economic vulnerability across the country. In Lagos, poverty is particularly concentrated in informal settlements, where two-thirds of residents live below the poverty line, and more than 70% reside in unplanned or informal housing lacking basic services (Amnesty International, 2025). These harsh socio-economic conditions compel many urban poor to seek livelihoods in the informal e-waste sector, including electronics scavenging, repair, and resale - activities that expose them to significant health and environmental risks.

More so, the perception that imported second-hand devices are more affordable or of higher quality than locally available products fuels a steady demand for used electronics from industrialized countries. Informal entrepreneurs in markets like Ikeja Computer Village profit by repairing and reselling these devices (Ovie, 2024; Babayemi et al., 2024; Ore, 2016; Omobowale, 2012; Ideho, 2012). When gadgets are beyond repair, they are stripped for parts and the remainder is dumped or burned, perpetuating the cycle of waste.

Another key driver is the lack of a robust indigenous electronics industry. Because Nigeria produces relatively few electronic devices domestically, consumers rely heavily on imports for ICT products (African Development

Bank [AfDB], 2024; Ogungbuyi et al., 2012; Ideho, 2012). Without local manufacturing to ensure longer-lasting products suited to the context, Lagos is flooded with used electronics that have short remaining lifespans. This tie into the global dynamic of rapid technological advancement and planned obsolescence. Developed nations frequently upgrade to newer models and dispose of old devices, which are then exported to countries like Nigeria. As manufacturers shorten product life cycles to drive consumption, the volume of discarded electronics flowing into Lagos increases (Johnson, 2023; Marshall, 2021; Rico, 2025). Each new smartphone or computer generation renders previous ones obsolete faster, contributing to an ever-accelerating accumulation of e-waste.

Insufficient public awareness and education also exacerbate the crisis. Many consumers and informal workers in Lagos are unaware of the toxic risks associated with improper e-waste disposal (Ezeudoka et al., 2024). Expired or damaged electronics are often reused or handled without precautions, leading to direct exposure to harmful chemicals.

Without adequate knowledge, individuals may not support or demand safer recycling practices, and communities may not pressure authorities for better waste management. This knowledge gap means grassroots communities remain vulnerable to e-waste's health impacts, as evidenced by studies linking poor handling techniques to local health issues (Ezeudoka et al., 2024; Azodo et al., 2017; Hossain et al., 2010).

Finally, weak governance and inadequate waste management infrastructure in Lagos allow the e-waste problem to proliferate. Formal recycling facilities and hazardous waste treatment plants are scarce (Johnson, 2023; UNEP, 2019; Rico, 2025; Marshall, 2021). Nigeria has ratified international agreements like the Basel Convention to prevent hazardous waste dumping, but enforcement is weak and corruption can undermine regulatory efforts (Johnson, 2023; UNEP, 2019; Rico, 2025). Financial incentives drive some officials or businesses to turn a blind eye to illegal e-waste imports (Johnson, 2023). Moreover, the absence of a coordinated e-waste collection and recycling system means that even well-intended policies have limited impact. Altogether, poverty, global electronic trade imbalances, technological change, low awareness, and regulatory failures collectively explain why Lagos is facing a daunting e-waste crisis.

Impacts of e-waste mismanagement on health and environment

The mismanagement of e-waste in Lagos has dire consequences for both human health and the environment. E-waste contains a cocktail of hazardous materials, and when devices are improperly dismantled

Figure 2. Key toxic elements and environmental contaminants released due to poor handling or illegal disposal of electronic waste (Ghulam and Abushammala, 2023).

or disposed of, these toxins are released into the ecosystem, negatively impacting the air, soil, water, and human health (Figure 2). Heavy metals like lead, cadmium, and mercury are commonly found in electronic components and pose serious health risks upon exposure. Lead, for example, can cause irreversible neurological damage in children and contribute to cardiovascular and kidney problems in adults (Abogunrin-Olafisoye and Adeyi, 2025; Okukpon, 2015). Cadmium exposure is linked to kidney dysfunction, bone weakness, and cancer, while mercury can convert to methylmercury in water and bioaccumulate in fish, leading to neurological and developmental harm in humans who consume contaminated seafood (Bankole et al., 2023; Isimekhai et al., 2017; Hossain et al., 2010; Okukpon, 2015). Field observations in Lagos's informal recycling sites have documented workers suffering from respiratory issues, skin disorders, and other ailments due to inhalation of fumes and direct contact with toxic waste (Oluwanifemi, 2025; Bankole et al., 2023; Omole et al., 2015). Long-term exposure to burning e-waste has been associated with elevated rates of lung disease and other chronic conditions in nearby communities.

Environmental impacts are equally alarming. Many e-waste components are non-biodegradable, meaning they persist in soil and water for decades. When e-waste is dumped in landfills or open fields, rainwater percolates through the waste and leaches heavy metals and

chemicals into the soil and groundwater. This contamination can render agricultural land infertile and pollute drinking water sources. Crops grown in contaminated soil absorb toxic substances, which then enter the food chain, posing risks to food security and health. Water bodies near e-waste dumpsites in Lagos have shown elevated levels of pollutants, affecting aquatic life. Fish and other marine organisms' bioaccumulate toxins like mercury and arsenic, leading to biodiversity loss and ecosystem disruption (Ole et al., 2024; Chowrimootoo, 2011).

Air pollution from e-waste is another critical issue: the open burning of circuit boards, cables, and plastics releases dioxins and furans, as well as greenhouse gases that contribute to climate change. Locally, these emissions cause problems such as acid rain and smog, further impacting human health and environmental quality. The economic toll of these environmental health problems is substantial. Healthcare costs associated with treating e-waste-related illnesses strain public health resources, and reduced agricultural productivity due to soil contamination affects food security (Abogunrin-Olafisoye and Adeyi, 2025; Okukpon, 2015). Furthermore, the long-term costs of environmental cleanup and remediation are often far higher than the costs of implementing proper waste management systems. Without intervention, the unchecked e-waste pollution in Lagos threatens to undermine the well-being of its

population and the integrity of its ecosystems, entrenching environmental injustice in the region.

Stakeholders and current management efforts

Addressing Lagos's e-waste problem involves multiple stakeholders, each with distinct roles and challenges. The government, through agencies like the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA), is responsible for policymaking and enforcement of e-waste regulations. Nigeria has developed some regulations, such as the National Environmental (Electrical/Electronic Sector) Regulations, 2022, and is a party to international treaties controlling hazardous waste trade (Ole et al., 2024). However, implementation in Lagos has been weak. Customs officials and port authorities often lack the resources or will to thoroughly inspect incoming containers, enabling unscrupulous importers to bring in banned electronic waste (Barnabas, 2025; UNEP, 2019). Periodic government initiatives to curb e-waste dumping have had limited success due to corruption, poor coordination, and the sheer volume of informally handled waste (Badawi, 2025; Okupkon, 2015).

The informal sector is the most visibly involved stakeholder group (Bankole et al., 2023; Ogwueleka and Naveen, 2021; Adeyi et al., 2019). Thousands of informal workers ("pickers" and recyclers) in Lagos depend on e-waste for their livelihood (UNEP, 2019). They operate in scrapyards and dumps, using unsafe techniques to extract valuable materials. Their activities, while hazardous, fill a gap left by insufficient formal waste collection services. Informal recyclers have created an efficient but dangerous economy around e-waste: they can outcompete formal recyclers by operating at low cost (avoiding taxes, proper waste disposal expenses, and worker protections) (UNEP, 2019). This competitive edge means that any solution must account for the socio-economic reality that these individuals rely on e-waste to survive. Simply banning informal recycling without providing alternatives could harm vulnerable communities.

Formal e-waste management companies do exist in Lagos, albeit in small number. Facilities such as E-Terra Technologies and Hinckley Recycling Nigeria Limited have been established to safely process electronic waste (Amuda, 2022). These companies partner with government and international organizations on pilot projects to develop a circular economy for electronics (Amuda, 2022; UNEP, 2019). For instance, the Circular Economy Approaches for the Electronics Sector project (funded by the Global Environment Facility) aims to integrate informal workers into formal operations by offering training, protective gear, and financial incentives (UNEP, 2019). However, formal recyclers currently handle only a small fraction of Lagos's e-waste, as they struggle

to compete with the informal sector on cost and scale. Their efforts are further hindered by limited investment, inadequate infrastructure for collection and transport of e-waste, and low public awareness about available recycling programs.

International stakeholders also play a role. Exporting countries and global manufacturers contribute to the e-waste flow into Lagos. The lack of extended producer responsibility (EPR) on a global scale means manufacturers are not accountable for their products at end-of-life, shifting the burden to importing countries (Adetuyi and Williams, 2022).

Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and international bodies like the UNEP are working to highlight the issue and support Nigeria's efforts through funding and expertise (as seen in UNEP's involvement with NESREA's projects). Yet, without stronger global cooperation and strict enforcement of e-waste trade laws, Lagos will continue to shoulder a disproportionate load of the world's electronic waste. Hence, the stakeholder landscape in Lagos's e-waste management includes a struggling regulatory system, a vast informal workforce, a nascent formal recycling industry, and international actors whose actions upstream affect local outcomes. So far, the misalignment of these stakeholders' capacities and interests has resulted in fragmented and insufficient management of the crisis.

Applying an earth-eco-socialist framework

Eco-Socialism: Linking ecology and social justice

Eco-socialism has emerged as a framework that merges ecological sustainability with socialist principles of equity and collective well-being. It originated in the late 20th-century "red-green" debates, essentially a synthesis of Marxist left and ecological left perspectives (Pillay, 2025). The core premise is that environmental degradation is inseparable from the capitalist system's prioritization of profit and perpetual growth at the expense of people and planet. Eco-socialist theorists argue that meaningful solutions to crises like pollution and climate change require transforming the socio-economic order into one that is democratic, equitable, and environmentally sustainable (Pillay, 2025; Huan, 2021).

In contrast to "green capitalist" approaches that tinker with technology while ignoring underlying social inequality, eco-socialism insists that issues of class, race, and imperialism must be addressed alongside ecological problems (Baer and Singer, 2023; Huan, 2021; Pillay, 2025). Indeed, contemporary eco-socialist thought is rooted in global struggles against what has been called the ravages of fossil-fueled capitalism, colonial dispossession, and patriarchy. Even in policy discourse, we see echoes of this perspective – for example, China's official concept of a "socialist eco-civilization" explicitly

rejects an eco-capitalist path and embeds environmental goals within a socialist vision of development (Huan, 2021).

Overall, eco-socialism represents a call for a “just transition” that tackles environmental and social injustices together. Scholars note that capitalism’s exploitative structures - often intertwined with racism and inequality - have produced a global “ecology of injustice” in which marginalized communities bear a disproportionate burden of pollution and harm (Barkdull and Harris, 2024). Some have even labeled the current era the “Wasteocene” to highlight how capitalist accumulation operates through waste and disposability, particularly affecting the Global South and communities of color (Armiero et al., 2023). In short, eco-socialism frames the environmental crisis as a symptom of the broader social crisis of capitalism, envisioning an alternative world system oriented around ecological care, social justice, and democratic control of resources.

Earth-Eco-Socialism: An African eco-socialist extension

Earth-Eco-Socialism is a paradigm developed by Ojomo (2019, 2024a, 2024b) and is now being applied to various issues (Mogaji, 2024), extends core eco-socialist ideas by infusing them with communal ethics and a more explicitly justice-oriented ecological stance that cares for nature as having intrinsic value. Writing from the Nigerian context, Ojomo (2024a) argues that environmental crises in Africa are fundamentally driven by capitalist practices that exploit both human and nonhuman entities. This concept (that is, Earth-Eco-Socialism) is based on the eco-socialist idea that capitalism systematically destroys the environment, and it adds a unique perspective by emphasizing communal values, caring relationships, and moral duties to both people and nature. Earth-Eco-Socialism recognizes the need to confront both the social and ecological roots of environmental problems in tandem.

In practice, this means social development and environmental protection must go hand-in-hand: any path to progress should simultaneously address social injustices (like poverty and inequality) and environmental degradation through democratic processes and robust legal frameworks. As Bookchin (2005: 426) observed, separating ecological problems from social problems or giving only token attention to their relationship “would be to grossly misconstrue the sources of the growing environmental crisis” - a principle that earth-eco-socialism incorporates. Issues such as global pollution, extreme poverty, and capitalist exploitation are seen as deeply interconnected under Earth-Eco-Socialism, requiring integrated solutions.

Notably, earth-eco-socialism challenges both unchecked capitalism *and* certain Western eco-centric

models by asserting that social justice for humans cannot be at the expense of the ecology, and that our sense of community must include the land, water, and non-human life (Orton, 2010). To further distinguish the vantage point of Earth-Eco-Socialism from traditional eco-socialism, the latter has at times remained overly anthropocentric or statist, whereas an Earth-Eco-Socialist ethic re-centers the Earth itself as a subject with intrinsic value and rights. A distinguishing feature of Earth-Eco-Socialism is its grounding in communal values. Earth-eco-socialism emphasizes the principle of cooperation and communal care as the bedrock of a sustainable society. In practical terms, this reflects a socialist moral attitude that is communalistic in nature - stressing solidarity, mutual aid, and the importance of meeting everyone’s needs within the community.

This position expresses the idea that that truly meaningful living and development emerge from a communitarian lifestyle hinged on consideration of others’ well-being, rather than on individualistic accumulation. This perspective resonates with philosophies like *Ubuntu* and other African ethics that prize the collective good (Pillay, 2025).

Earth-Eco-Socialism is thus as much an ethical paradigm as a political one: it calls for cultivating an ecological conscience - a moral commitment to care for all species and the Earth as a whole. Hence, earth-eco-socialism is a moral (rather than purely political) defense of the rights of both humans and the land, embracing socialism as a value system that promotes the collective good, social solidarity, and care for the biotic community. In effect, Earth-Eco-Socialism seeks to correct the dominant “development” narrative by rejecting the global model that has allowed Western corporations and elites to degrade African environments and communities with impunity. Instead, it demands a new paradigm of development rooted in justice: one where ecological well-being and social equity are co-equal goals, and where those traditionally marginalized, both people *and* ecosystems, are placed at the center of ethical concern. By integrating communal ethics and an eco-centric vision into eco-socialism, Earth-Eco-Socialism offers a holistic blueprint for addressing environmental crises in the Global South - one that explicitly counters the legacy of Western Europe’s exploitative relationship with African land and people, and advocates for equitable stewardship of nature.

Applying Earth-Eco-Socialism to Lagos’s e-waste crisis

Lagos State’s e-waste crisis exemplifies the very dynamics Earth-Eco-Socialism is built to confront: a toxic convergence of global capitalist excess, weak environmental governance, and social inequality. Mountains of discarded electronics from industrialized

countries have been “externalized” to Lagos’s markets and dumps, where impoverished communities and informal workers bear the health and environmental burdens. An Earth-Eco-Socialist framework approaches this situation not as an isolated technical problem, but as a symptom of deeper structural injustices in how society produces and values waste. Applying the framework to Lagos means realigning both policies and social values in line with ecological care and social justice. Concretely, several transformative strategies can be envisioned:

Communal ownership and ethical stewardship of e-waste recycling

Earth-Eco-Socialism would urge a shift away from profit-driven, informal handling of e-waste toward communal or public control of e-waste management. This could involve creating state-supported recycling centers run on nonprofit principles or cooperative models, wherein workers and local communities have ownership stakes. By formalizing the currently informal workforce into cooperatives or public enterprises, Lagos can ensure safer recycling practices, fair labor conditions, and a shared responsibility for environmental health. Such an approach puts into practice the ideal of collective stewardship of resources - in this case, treating electronic waste as a public concern to be managed for the common good rather than as an externality to be exploited by a few. It echoes Earth-Eco-Socialism’s emphasis on empowering the community to govern environmental resources ethically and equitably. For example, a cooperative of former e-waste pickers could be trained and equipped to recover valuable materials in regulated facilities, combining their grassroots expertise with improved technology and safety measures. This would not only reduce pollution and health hazards, but also provide dignified “green” jobs, illustrating how environmental and social aims can be met simultaneously under a socialist ethic of care.

Corporate accountability and restructured global engagement

An Earth-Eco-Socialist solution in Lagos would also tackle the transnational dimension of the e-waste problem by holding producers and wealthy nations accountable. In line with eco-socialist critiques of capitalism’s throwaway culture, policies should force electronics manufacturers and exporter countries to take responsibility for their products’ end-of-life impacts. This can be achieved through extended producer responsibility laws, import bans on non-functional electronics, and international agreements compelling exporters to reclaim or fund the recycling of e-waste they generate. By legally mandating that corporations

internalize the environmental costs currently foisted onto Nigeria, the flood of hazardous waste into Lagos can be curbed. Also, anti-consumerist measures championed by Earth-Eco-Socialism such as banning planned obsolescence in device design and enshrining a “right to repair” would extend the lifespan of electronics and reduce waste generation at its source. These reforms align with the framework’s core principle of sustainability over profit: instead of allowing multinationals to maximize profit by selling short-lived gadgets and dumping the consequences on poorer communities, production would be guided by durability, reparability, and recyclability (values that protect both people and planet). Implementing such measures in Lagos, supported by global cooperation, would represent a justice-oriented intervention, demanding that those who benefit from electronics also bear the responsibility for their safe disposal, rather than shifting the burden onto vulnerable populations.

Environmental justice and participatory governance

Finally, Earth-Eco-Socialism calls for centering the voices and needs of those most affected by environmental hazards. In Lagos, this means that residents of e-waste hotspots (such as Alaba Market or the Olusosun dump community) should have a meaningful role in shaping e-waste policy. Community-based environmental committees, for instance, could partner with local authorities and experts to monitor pollution, devise safer waste-handling practices, and ensure accountability for any ongoing dumping or burning. Such decentralized; grassroots governance reflects the framework’s commitment to deep democracy and communal empowerment in environmental decision-making. Moreover, an Earth-Eco-Socialist approach insists on reparative justice: the idea that remediation of environmental damage must include compensation and support for affected communities. Thus, Lagos could push for international aid or restitution from the countries and companies that have used its territory as an e-waste destination.

This might involve securing funds for medical care for poisoned workers, cleanup of contaminated soil and water, and investments in sustainable local enterprises as alternative livelihoods. The underlying principle is that the burdens of pollution should not fall solely on the poorest communities simply because they are marginalized in the world economy; instead, those who generated and profited from the waste stream bear responsibility for rectifying the harm. By advocating such fairness, Earth-Eco-Socialism operationalizes the notion that environmental justice is a crucial pillar of sustainability where the rights of people and the integrity of ecosystems are interdependent, and both must be safeguarded in unison.

Conclusion

The e-waste crisis in Lagos is not merely a technical or logistical challenge; it is a deeply rooted social and ecological injustice shaped by global capitalism, weak governance, and systemic inequality. This paper has shown that Earth-Eco-Socialism offers a compelling ethical and political framework for addressing these intertwined issues. By integrating communal values with eco-socialist principles, Earth-Eco-Socialism reframes e-waste not as an inevitable byproduct of modernization, but as a consequence of unjust systems that prioritize profit over people and planet. Applying this paradigm to Lagos reveals practical pathways toward justice: communal ownership of waste infrastructure, corporate accountability for transnational pollution, and participatory environmental governance. These interventions collectively demonstrate that environmental sustainability and social equity are not only compatible but mutually reinforcing.

Ultimately, this study calls for a paradigm shift that reimagines development, waste, and community from a place of moral responsibility to both humanity and the Earth.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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